

Kinetic Studies of Transition Metal Ions on Stannic Oxide

J. P. RAWAT* and B. SINGH

Department of Chemistry, Aligarh Muslim University, Aligarh-202 001

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The kinetics of exchange reactions of Fe^{III}, Co^{II}, Mn^{II} and Zn^{II} ions on stannic oxide has been studied at four different temperatures (30, 40, 50 and 60°). At concentrations > 0.1 M, the rate of exchange is governed by particle-diffusion mechanism and it is confirmed by Bt vs t plot. The diffusion coefficient, activation energy, entropy of activation and free energy of activation are calculated.

STUDIES in the field of inorganic ion-exchangers are increasing due to their selectivity and stability under certain conditions. To understand the theoretical aspects of ion-exchange separations it is essential to study the thermodynamics and kinetics of this process. The kinetic studies on ion-exchangers were mainly started by Nachod and Wood¹. Nancollas and Peterson² described the quantitative measurement on hydrous thoria and zirconia. Studies on cerium(IV) phosphate³ have also been reported. The kinetic studies on tantalum arsenate⁴, ferric antimonate⁵ and stannic arsenate⁶ described the theoretical aspects of the chemical separations. Only few studies on stannic oxide as an ion-exchanger have been reported⁷. In the present work the kinetic parameters on stannic oxide are described.

Experimental

Stannic oxide was synthesised⁸ by the reaction of nitric acid and tin metal. After washing and drying it was finely ground and sieved to the particles of mesh size 50–100, 100–150, 150–200 and 200–300. For various studies the particles of mean radius 100 μm (British Standard) were used. Solutions of constant ionic strength were taken in the stoppered conical flasks. The exchanger (0.2 g) was thermostated with the metal ion solution (20 ml) at 30, 40, 50 and 60° ($\pm 1^\circ$). After appropriate time intervals, contents of the flasks were filtered and titrated with EDTA.

Results and Discussion

Conditions were set for the particle-diffusion and to ensure particle-diffusion mechanism experiments were carried out at concentrations > 0.1 M. At concentrations < 0.01 M, the rate of exchange depends on the concentration of the metal ions in the external solution and the process is governed by film diffusion as the plots of Bt vs t were not straight lines.

The values of F at different time intervals and different temperatures were obtained for Fe^{III}, Co^{II},

Mn^{II} and Zn^{II} exchanges. The fractional attainment of equilibrium (F) is the ratio of exchange at time t to exchange at equilibrium. These results show that the rate of exchange is directly proportional to temperature. Bt vs t plots at four different temperatures are presented in Fig. 1. Equations given by Boyd *et al.*⁹ and improved by Reichenberg¹⁰ were used for evaluating the kinetic parameters where

$$B = \pi^2 D_i / r^2 \quad (1)$$

Fig. 1. Effect of temperature on the rate of exchange for $\text{Mn}^{2+} - \text{H}^+$ on stannic oxide.

where, B is the slope of plot Bt vs t , D_i the effective diffusion coefficient and r the particle radius. In all the cases the plots of Bt vs t are straight lines

passing through the origin which indicates that the rate determining step is particle-diffusion at all the temperatures. The values of B derived by the least-square method are given in Table 1. To study the effect of particle size on the rate of exchange, plot of B against $1/r^2$ comes the straight line indicating that the rate of exchange is inversely proportional to the square of particle radius (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Plot of β vs $1/r^2$ for Fe^{3+} at 30° .

TABLE 1— B VALUES AS A FUNCTION OF TEMPERATURE AND PARTICLE SIZE

Metal ion	r μm	$B \times 10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$			
		30°	40°	50°	60°
Fe^{III}	100	1.66	2.00	2.25	2.49
Fe^{III}	60	2.00	—	—	—
Fe^{III}	43	2.33	—	—	—
Fe^{III}	30	2.91	—	—	—
Co^{II}	100	1.16	1.37	1.54	1.66
Mn^{II}	100	0.95	1.12	1.29	1.37
Zn^{II}	100	0.62	0.74	0.83	0.95

The effective diffusion coefficient D_1 was calculated from equation (1) and linear relationship between $\log D_1$ and $1/T$ enables the calculation of the energy of activation (E_a) using the Arrhenius equation,

$$D_1 = D_0 \exp(-E_a/RT) \quad (2)$$

The values of E_a (Table 2) show no regular trend with the ionic size values of D_0^{11} , and D_1 were obtained by extrapolating and interpolating the plots (Fig. 3) of

$$D_0 = 2.72 d^2 kT/h \exp(\Delta S^*/R) \quad (3)$$

where, d is the ionic jump distance (equal to $5 \text{ \AA}$), k the Boltzman constant (equal to $1.38 \times 10^{-23} \text{ K}^{-1}$

Fig. 3. $\log D_1$ vs $1/T$ for (●) Fe^{3+} , (Δ) Co^{3+} , (○) Mn^{3+} , and ($\blacktriangle$) Zn^{3+} .

mol^{-1}), h the Planck constant and T was 303 K. The values of ΔS^* are negative. The values of ΔG^* were obtained from the values of E_a and ΔS^* .

TABLE 2—SELF-DIFFUSION COEFFICIENT, ENERGY OF ACTIVATION, ENTROPY OF ACTIVATION AND FREE ENERGY OF ACTIVATION OF METAL IONS ON STANNIC OXIDE (100 μm)

Metal ion	D_0 m s^{-1}	E_a kJ mol^{-1}	ΔS^* $\text{J K}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$	ΔG^* kJ mol^{-1}
Fe^{III}	1.69×10^{-10}	11.60	-85.42	37.35
Co^{II}	3.16×10^{-11}	8.05	-202.04	69.25
Mn^{II}	4.36×10^{-11}	9.41	-94.71	38.10
Zn^{II}	6.91×10^{-11}	11.70	-90.88	39.23

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